

Review Article

Book Review: “Governing Climate Change”

Mohammed B. E. Saaida

Department of International Relations & Diplomacy, Faculty of administration sciences, Al-Istiqlal University, Jericho - Palestine

Book Review

Governing Climate Change. London: by Harriet Bulkeley and Peter Newell. (Routledge. 2010. ISBN 978-0-415-46769-8, xix + 142 pages).

Harriet Bulkeley is Reader in the Department of Geography at Durham University, UK.

Peter Newell is Professor of International Development at the University of East Anglia, UK.

The "*Governing Climate Change*" book by Bulkeley and Newell is part of Routledge's series of global institutions. It addresses the climate change governance issues that occurred significantly through the last two decades in the field of international relations. The issues hit strongly the relationships and interests between all the countries over the world, in particular the industrialized, non-industrialized, and the newly industrialized countries. The countries were mainly divided into two sides; the North modern countries and the South developing countries.

As a matter of fact, climate change came out with undeniable challenging sequences, which had been observed, tested and recorded by scientists, such as global warming, desertification, floods and storms. The emission of CO₂ and chlorofluorocarbon gases resulting from the accelerating process of industry are the main factors. The good side of humanity occurred in the multilateral efforts that had been put together to admit the merging danger, to face it, stop it, and to cure its sequences in innovative ways. The other no good side is guided and ruled by the nations' interests for economic prosperity and political dominance.

The strength of the book of *Governing Climate Change* written by Harriet Bulkeley and Peter Newell is found crucial questions of effectiveness through delineation of new governance actors and dynamics combined with their analysis of the challenges that these arrangements face. The book's chapters map aspects of the governance landscape also address how new types of governance raise and deal with, accountability, and equity.

In this book we see a trial to highlight and follow the efforts of international collaboration regarding taking real effective measurements, the key actors, the role of each and what had been done till the book is published. It ends with a summary of the authors' main findings leading to a comprehensive final understanding of the concepts toward the climate change governance and the supposed key actors' role in future.

This book with 114 pages is spotting the light on the concepts of climate change governance. The authors are giving up-to dated perspective to achieve real governance according to multilateral treaties. It addresses climate change, interactions at all levels starting from individual behavior, policy development and practice, large-scale structures of political-economic and technological systems which all will be involved in the coming years, as they hope to be done. The authors have addressed the international agreements, conferences, and conventions to review the obstacles and reasons behind delaying effective climate change governance.

The authors are discussing and analyzing the climate politics through the debate on the nature of international relation between governments as basic actors and non-governmental organization regarding who holds the responsibility for governing the climate change. And which institutions have or shall take a kind of power to manage the processes over the sovereignty of states and what tools might be implemented. The equity between North and South is put into the discussion also.

The book which consists of six chapters starts with a typical opening with a historical summary to drag the readers and scholars into the background of climate change governance for more understanding of the question's roots, and also to show the development of the climate change regime in early international responses. It shows in analysis how all actors, including scientists and international institutions engaged into environmental politics via rounds of negotiations and thinking to find convincing methods to all parts to reduce the emission of dioxide carbon into the atmosphere. The growing participations of governmental and none governmental organization is an important party on the table of negotiations. But still, no power can be used against any country to reach the demanded reduction of emission rate. Even withdrawal is practiced by the United States of America form Kyoto Protocol in 2001 claiming that the predicted advantages are less than the disadvantages.

The international community managed to hold several important conferences and reports regarding the governing climate change. The world started in 1988 by the World Conference on the changing Atmosphere where politicians and scientists concluded that "Humanity is conducting and unintended, uncontrolled, globally pervasive experiment whose ultimate consequences could be second only to nuclear war". The conference recommended reducing CO₂ emission by 20 percent by 2005. In 1990 the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) published its first Assessment Report. The United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) had been signed by 154 countries at the United Nation in 1992. Many more successful and unsuccessful gatherings were held later till 2009. Kyoto Protocol is one of the most important. More than 150 countries signed it. It binds 38 industrialized countries to reduce Green House Gas (GHG) emission by average of 5.2 percent below 1990 levels during the period 2008 – 2012.

Governing for whom? Equity, justice, and the politics of sustainable development, the two writers are searching the responsibility of the actors in the global pollution warming and causes of unequal world. The socioeconomic and political North-South division is directly applied to climate change governance. Historically, the northern countries emitted high rate of CO₂emissions more than the southern countries. The questions of social justice and equity still are clearly observed in all efforts made to challenge climate change sequences. The issue of injustice and equity is getting more complexity due to several factors where the development of some southern countries is the most important of them.

All actors are giving different definitions of the problem in following their interests. Coalitions already are made the thing that leads for incoherent strategies and measures. The main point here is that all nation-states are forced to enter the game as an essential component of their external policy, but they want to have the biggest benefits with the lowest cost. Transnational networks and the relation between global and local in governing climate change emerged in environmental political arena as inevitable result of globalization. The writers believed that multi-levels partnerships in governing climate change are encouraged between individuals, families, local authorities, private sector, public sector, none-state organizations and nation-state organizations. It has to keep going increasingly in the coming future.

Transitional climate change governance arrangements involve a whole host of actors-from municipal government to private foundations, non-government organizations to multinational corporations. These networks take on different characteristics depending on whether they are constituted by public actor, private actors, or hybrid of public and private actors.

The public transitional governance includes regional or state authorities, or local governments, municipal networks such as the New EnglandGovernor and the East Canadian Premiers (NEGECP) 2001 initiative to adapt a joint climate change plan.

The hybrid involves actors from public and private spheres in various forms of collaboration. This form of partnership is an important feature of the transnational climate change governance landscape. The Kyoto Protocol flexible mechanism made it easy to form such active networks.

The self-regulation and governance initiatives contribute to the emergence of the "new global public domain". Private transitional governance involves a variety of non-state actors, including corporate and civil society sectors. In arrangements through which issues are defined, rules are made, and compliance with these rules is monitored beyond the direct supervision of nation-states or other actors from the public sphere.

Community sharing in governing of climate change by moving from ignorance to expertise has a great effect. It is the basic level of governing and a worldwide contribution. The experiment of the United Kingdom presents an excellent example of community Climate change governance. Since the year 2000, the British government has started a series of government-funded programs such as the Community Renewable Initiative and Clear Skies. Private sector got involved in the process. This was accompanied with awareness campaigns and encouraging low taxes to be paid in case of participation.

The barriers that face individuals are summarized in lack of knowledge, uncertainty, no trust in information sources, externalizing responsibility, and reliance on technology. So, the climate change is perceived as a distant threat, the importance of other personal priorities, reluctance to change lifestyle, fatalism and helplessness. The social barriers are due to the lack of actions by governments, business and industry, the pressure of social norms and expectations and lack of enabling initiatives.

The book brings the discussion back to major issues of what is new in governing climate change and the ways in which the experience of climate change governance expands our broader understanding of global politics and governance.

The authors present an analysis to the current situation of climate change governance. The ideas and point views they show make it clear that they are scholars in the field of environmental policy and but not scientists of climate change. They are not getting into deep details of scientific techniques and methods that could be followed. But, their vision is great. Let the whole world get involved in governing the climate change and make it easy for all.

The book message is important and clear: **In the future, the nations should work together to save the planet from global warming through sharing responsibility in justice and equally. Involve all levels of all nations, spread awareness and share knowledge and experience among them "**.

The book is a valuable contribution to the scholarly literature in environmental policy. The authors presented a clear analysis showing operations of climate change governance by traditional actors reaching the local communities and private sector participation. It clarifies the major problems which stand in the way of achieving effective environmental policy facing the risks of climate change. Political and economic dominance with less commitment are clear to be seen, but not declared officially. From the local level to international level are demanded to cooperate. The nations-states have the power to take decisions and enforce them. Non-state actors such as international institutions and intercontinental firms form vital and active role in contributing climate governance. Laws must be changed in order to meet the requirements of each state, locally and internationally.

The book is condensed of essential topics. It cannot be enough to go into details within 114 medium size pages. The writers' goals and directions are the correct ones. Climate change does challenge conventional understanding of governance and politics and our scholarship and teaching must adjust to this reality. The main goal is to do re-conceptualization itself and outlining the scholarly and practical challenges inherent in the new perspective is the accomplishment both sought and achieved rather than doing deep analyzing the dynamics just mentioned which is not the goal of the book. Further, it is achieved in a way that is useful for both students and scholars seeking to understand where the study of global climate governance needs to go.

There is a big shift in the numbers and quality of actors in governing climate change due to more understanding and increasing awareness. Investments in green energy are observed. Also the programs funded by the World Bank and other international organizations in Asia and Latin America put an additional factor of raising awareness among people.

The problem: how to do coordination between all levels to avoid duplications in role internationally and at national level. International consensus on concepts is a must. Finding a super intelligent method and mechanism to determine what, who, why, where to expend the fund and how.

The theoretical approach which had been presented in this book provided partial clarification of a main case of international negotiations. The book recommends to open question for further needed developments of theories that can be more appropriate for the explanation of the rules of international open access regimes. The authors went through the political economy approach in discussing for understanding of powers that form political-economic coalitions. They emphasized in particular the role of economic actors where powerful interests are the stake and form as change ultimately has to come.

In this book, the writers have undertaken a comprehensive assessment of the international responses to climate change governance by focusing on its most visible results, namely the UN Framework Convention on Climate Change and other international conferences in concern.

The World Bank is an increasingly central actor in climate governance, not primarily because of its role in developing the Prototype Carbon Fund or the Climate Investment Fund, but because it exerts such influence overall development strategies of many developing countries.

The environmental-political process produced the formation of UNFCCC due to the strategic coordination on the international level to control the anticipated changes to the global climate system caused by human interference with the atmosphere. Much international pressure was practiced in order

to do such important international environmental agreement and to implement it.

The ultimate best results of any international negotiations do not mean that the agreements will be followed by the various parties. Self-interests will remain the main motive for the actors involved in a limited percentage in the agreements. Even more, the full obligation of sincere parties to abide by the rules of the agreements, there is no guarantee that it will reach its goals, mainly when complexity of environmental phenomena is engaged.

The book is written for scholars and researchers who will get benefit from it. Actually, ordinary people cannot read it easily unless they have a very well knowledge and a very good background of climate change governance and problems, from one hand. From the other hand the readers should be aware of the international efforts that had been made to face climate change. And the essential thing that the readers must be a quite knowing about international relations and politics.

The "Governing Climate Change" book deserves to be read by scholars of political science. It is designed for scholars interested in climate change governance. A background for readers is a must. I saw that it did not go through or address several important issues that are related directly to the climate change such as:

1. The book presents a case of prediction of the coming future, "how climate change governance should be". It does not present practical and detailed mechanisms of international relation on climate change. It does not go into the deep details of the mechanisms of how the countries will do against the challenges of global climate change effects. How to come over the economic obstacles of the developing countries.
2. The world's population growth and its effect on the climate change. This is a very important issue because it means more demand for energy.
3. The book does not present a deep analysis for the real situations of the developing countries regarding economy growth. How the mechanism of reducing CO₂ emission will affect their plans of development in the of technology shortage.
4. The book should contain figures, illustrations and more realistic examples that makes easy for readers for more understanding. This matter is related directly to science. Figures and charts are important.
5. The book is written from a western point of view.

Citation:

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